

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

OIL CONTENT IN SOYBEAN SEEDS BY NMR RELAXATION METHOD

Kharchuk O.,

*Doctor of biological sciences,
Moldova State University,*

Institute of Genetics, Physiology and Plant Protection,

Maliu A.,

*Doctor of biological sciences,
Moldova State University,*

Institute of Genetics, Physiology and Plant Protection

Kistol M.

Researcher,

Moldova State University,

Institute of Genetics, Physiology and Plant Protection

Abstract

Some of the data on the soybean seeds oil content were obtained by nondestructive NMR relaxation method for conditions of rainfed soybean fields. After harvest 2021 the minimal oil content was in the seeds of soybean variety Pentata ($14,6 \pm 0,2\%$ for the seeds with dry weight 100-150 mg and $14,9 \pm 0,4\%$ for the seeds with dry weight 200-250 mg) and the maximal oil content was in seeds of soybean variety Ladutsa ($19,3 \pm 0,3\%$ for the seeds with dry weight 100-150 mg and $19,7 \pm 0,5\%$ for the seeds with dry weight 150-200 mg). The oil content in seeds increases upon insufficient water provision of rainfed soybean field (Pentata, 2020 and 2022): 18-19% for the seeds with dry weight 100-250 mg.

Keywords: soybean seeds, oil content, RMN relaxation, rainfed field.

Seed oil content is important in the study of the genetic diversity of soybean. Cultivated soybean seeds have an oil content of approximately 18–22%, whereas wild soybean seeds contain about 8–10% oil [Patil G. et al., 2018]. Severe drought may change soybean seed oil content [D. L. Dornbos Jr. & R. E. Mullen, 1992]. The variations in oil contents of seed were attributed largely to the differential rainfall during the seed filling stage [Vollmann J. et al., 2000]. In the conditions of Mississippi State University (USA, 33°28' N, 88°47' W) the oil content of soybean seeds was 20,2-22,5% in the pot experiments with 10 soybean varieties [Poudel S. et al., 2023]. In the conditions of Brasil for various soybean varieties the oil content of soybean seeds was 12-20% in the pot and field experiments [Filho M.M. et al, 2001]

The aim of our work was to evaluate the oil content in soybean seeds of some varieties in 2020, 2021 and 2022 (different rainfall conditions).

The studies were carried out in 2020 -2022 at the fields of the Institute of Genetics, Physiology and Plant Protection (IGFPP), in soybean cenoses with traditional cultivation technology (400×10^3 plants/ha, row spacing 45 cm) with the different maturity group (MG) varieties: Pentata (MG III) and Ladutsa (MG II). To assess meteorological conditions was used the relative precipitation index (*RPI*) - the ratio of precipitation sum for the given period *P* and the long term average for the same period \bar{P} expressed in percent, $RPI = P/\bar{P} \times 100\%$;

for long period (from quarter to year) are such criteria of *RPI* value: 0-49,9% (extremely dry), 50,0-74,9% (very dry), 75,0-89,9% (dry) and 90,0-110,0% (average) [Kaczorowska Z., 1962; Bąk B., Łabęcki L., 2002].

After the discovery in 1946 of the phenomenon of nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), this method has also been used to determine the oil content in seeds. The use for biochemical purpose of the physical method, nuclear magnetic resonance and its improvement allow to do numerous rapid determinations of seed oil content during short period and significantly improve performance of analysis. Determination of oil content in seeds by NMR relaxation method is a clear, non-destructive, fast and accurate alternative to traditional liquid chemistry methods. The oil content determined by NMR relaxation method strictly corresponds to the amount of oil extracted from the seeds by organic solvents [Беликов И.Ф., Сазоненко М.К., 1966] and that is why the NMR relaxation method for determination of seed oil content is one of the international standards [ISO 5511:1992 (en), ISO 10565:1998]. The technique is applicable for sufficiently dry seeds, for soybeans - no more than 14% water.

Table 1 shows the data on water content in seeds for oil content determination by NMR relaxation method.

Table 1

Water content in seeds for oil content determination by NMR relaxation method

Variety	Harvest year	Water content, % dry weight
Pentata	2020	10,0±0,4
Pentata	2021	11,2±0,3
Pentata	2022	13,3±0,3
Ladutsa	2021	9,0±0,0

Due to longer storage the water content in more aged seeds of Pentata variety (harvest 2020 and 2021) was less than those of harvest 2022.

The NMR measurements were performed on individual seeds. The oil content of seeds was determined

by comparing echo-signal amplitudes from seeds with echo-signal amplitudes of calibration standards with different oil contents in glass chips.

Figure 1 shows the calibration standards for oil content determination by NMR relaxation.

Figure 1. Some of the standards with different oil content in glass chips. For calibration was used soybean oil, obtained from soybean seeds soybean Bucuria, harvested in 2011. The oil from the seeds was obtained from soybean meal after two extractions by toluene.

The data on oil content in seeds of soybean varieties Ladutsa and Pentata (harvest 2021) are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The oil content in soybean seeds of Pentata and Ladutsa varieties (harvest 2021). Each dot corresponds to a separate individual seed.

Table 2 shows the data on oil content determination by NMR relaxation method for different groups according the seed weight.

Table 2

Variety	Individual seed weight, <i>mg</i>		Oil content, % <i>dry weight</i>
	range	average	
Pentata	100-150	128±4	14,6±0,2
	150-200	177±2	14,8±0,2
	200-250	214±5	14,9±0,4
	250-300	269±16	15,0±0,3
Ladutsa	100-150	123±4	19,3±0,3
	150-200	157±2	19,7±0,5

Based on the relationship between precipitation and potential evapotranspiration for Chisinau [Potop V., Boroneant C., 2014] with a view to biological particularities of soybean ontogenesis, have been analyzed the meteorological conditions of the soybean growing year for 8-months (from 1/09 last year to 30/04 of the harvest year) and 10-months (from 1/09 last year to 30/06 of the harvest year) periods. According to long-term average data for these periods, 326 and 444 mm of precipitation falls in Chisinau. For 2021 soybean seeds 8-months value (September 2020/April 2021) was 309 mm and 10-months value (September 2020/June 2021) was 450 mm. In meteorological terms

[Kaczorowska Z., 1962; Bąk B., Łabędski L., 2002] the indicated periods of moisture accumulation for the seeds of the 2021 harvest were characterized by an *RPI* value of 95 and 101% (average).

Based on the meteorological data of 2021, from the data of Table 2 it follows that under normal conditions of water supply, soybean seeds of the Pentata variety are characterized by a lower oil content compared to the Ladutsa variety: 15 and 19%, respectively (by dry weight of seeds).

Data on the oil content in the seeds of soybean variety Pentata (harvest 2020, 2021 and 2022) are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The oil content in soybean seeds of Pentata variety, harvest 2020, 2021 and 2022. Each dot corresponds to a separate individual seed.

Table 3 shows the data on oil content in seeds Pentata variety (harvest 2020, 2021 and 2022) for different groups according the seed weight.

Table 3

Oil content in seeds of different weight for soybean variety Pentata (harvest 2020, 2021 and 2022)

Harvest year	Individual seed weight, mg		Oil content, % dry weight
	range	average	
2020	100-150	119±4	18,2±0,3
	150-200	173±5	19,2±0,3
	200-250	216±2	18,2±0,3
2021	100-150	128±4	14,6±0,2
	150-200	177±2	14,8±0,2
	200-250	214±5	14,9±0,4
	250-300	269±16	15,0±0,3
2022	100-150	136±4	18,0±0,3
	150-200	174±3	18,2±0,2
	200-250	209±2	18,6±0,4

Based on the relationship between precipitation and potential evapotranspiration for Chisinau [Potop V., Boroneant C., 2014] with a view to biological particularities of soybean ontogenesis, have been analyzed the meteorological conditions of the soybean growing year for 8-months (from 1/09 last year to 30/04 of the harvest year) and 10-months (from 1/09 last year to 30/06 of the harvest year) periods. According to long-term average data for these periods, 326 and 444 mm of precipitation falls in Chisinau. For 2021 soybean seeds 10-months value (September 2020/June 2021) was 450 mm, and for 2020 and 2022 soybean seeds these values were 258 and 196 mm. In meteorological terms [Kaczorowska Z., 1962; Bąk B., Łabędski L., 2002] the indicated period of moisture accumulation for the seeds of the 2021 harvest was characterized by an *RPI* value of 101% (average), and for the seeds of the 2020 and 2022 harvest – by an *RPI* value of 58% (dry) and 44% (extremely dry).

For 2020 and 2022 soybean seeds 8-months meteorological values were 108 and 168 mm. In meteorological terms [Kaczorowska Z., 1962; Bąk B., Łabędski L., 2002] the indicated periods of moisture accumulation for the seeds of the 2021 harvest were characterized by an *RPI* value of 101% (average), and for the seeds of the 2020 and 2022 harvest – by an *RPI* value of 33% (extremely dry) and 52% (dry). Insufficient precipitation over 8 months of moisture accumulation (September 2021/April 2022) continued in May and June 2022 (21 and 7 mm, respectively) and resulted in severe meteorological drought for 10-months period (September 2021-June 2022) with an *RPI* of 44%.

Based on the meteorological data for 2020, 2021 and 2022, it follows from the data in Table 3 that soybean seeds of the Pentata variety under normal conditions of moisture supply (2021) are characterized by a reduced oil content compared to the conditions of extremely severe drought (2020 and 2022): respectively, 15 and 18-19% on dry seed weight.

Conclusion

The minimal oil content in seeds was determined for soybean variety Pentata at harvest 2021 – 14,6-15,0% dry weight (14,6±0,2% for the seeds with dry weight 100-150 mg and 14,9±0,4% for the seeds with dry weight 200-250 mg). The maximal oil content in seeds was determined for soybean variety Ladutsa at harvest 2021 – 19,3-19,7% dry weight (19,3±0,3% for

the seeds with dry weight 100-150 mg and 19,7±0,5% for the seeds with dry weight 150-200 mg).

The oil content in seeds soybean variety Pentata increased upon insufficient water provision of rainfed soybean field. After harvest 2020 (*RPI* 33% for period from 01.09.2021 until 30.04.2022 corresponds to extremely severe meteorological drought) oil content in seeds of this variety became higher (than after harvest 2021) - 18,2±0,3% for the seeds with dry weight 100-150 mg and 200-250 mg; and 19,2±0,3% for the seeds with dry weight 150-200 mg. After harvest 2022 (*RPI* 44% for period from 01.09.2021 until 30.06.2022 corresponds to extremely severe meteorological drought) oil content in seeds of this variety became higher (than after harvest 2021) - 18,0-18,6% dry weight (18,0±0,3% for the seeds with dry weight 100-150 mg and 18,6±0,4% for the seeds with dry weight 200-250 mg).

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